

Workshop - Unlocking Potential: Strategies for Motivating and Engaging Shy, Quiet, Introverted Students in Engineering Education

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Abstract

Motivating and engaging shy, quiet, introverted students in engineering education requires a thoughtful, inclusive approach that fosters confidence and active participation. These students often prefer reflection over spontaneous speaking, making it crucial to provide diverse engagement opportunities. This workshop aims to equip engineering faculty and people interested in engineering student engagement with practical strategies to foster motivation, confidence, and engagement among shy, quiet, introverted students in engineering programs. By understanding their unique learning needs, instructors can create inclusive learning environments that encourage active participation and academic success. In this workshop, we intend to introduce some studies and active learning strategies available to motivate and engage shy, quiet, introverted engineering students. More important than that, we intend to discuss with participants how to create a safe and supportive environment for engineering students who are shy, quiet, or introverted; how to offer alternative participation strategies; which active learning strategies participants already use to motivate and engage their shy, quiet, introverted engineering students; how technology can help motivate and engage engineering students. This workshop has as its main objective to empower educators to unlock the full potential of all engineering students, regardless of their level of extroversion, shyness or quietness, ensuring a more inclusive and effective learning experience.

Keywords: Engagement; Motivation; Shyness; Quietness; Active Learning; Engineering Education.

1 Introduction

In the landscape of higher education, especially within demanding and collaborative fields like engineering, student engagement and motivation are widely recognized as essential components of academic success (Chen, Lattuca, & Hamilton, 2008; Zepke, & Leach, 2010; Groccia, 2018; Kunicina, Caiko, & Grants, 2023). Active learning approaches—ranging from group problem-solving to peer instruction and project-based learning—have become cornerstones of modern engineering pedagogy due to their proven benefits in enhancing comprehension, retention, and critical thinking (Smith, Sheppard, Johnson, & Johnson, 2005; Jiménez, & Andersson, 2012; Fernandes, Mesquita, Flores, & Lima, 2014; Aji, & Khan, 2019; Prince, Felder, & Brent, 2020; Munna, & Kalam, 2021; Gamarra, Dominguez, Velazquez, & Páez, 2022).

However, such approaches often come with the implicit expectation of visible, vocal participation. This presents a challenge for a specific and often overlooked population: shy, quiet and/or introverted students. These learners, who may be highly reflective, intellectually capable, and intrinsically motivated, often struggle to thrive in environments that prioritize extroversion and verbal assertiveness (Medaille, & Usinger, 2020). Their internal engagement can be mistakenly perceived as detachment or lack of interest, especially when engagement is measured primarily by classroom participation or leadership in group settings.

There are many theories about motivation and engagement, but discussing these theories is not the purpose of this workshop. The main objective of this workshop is to discuss Active Learning through an inclusive lens as it pertains to shy, overly quiet and/or introverted students. Active learning is defined by student-centered, participatory approaches that emphasize doing and thinking over passive reception. While powerful, many

active learning strategies — such as think-pair-share, peer instruction, jigsaw, case studies, among others — can become barriers if they are not intentionally designed to accommodate different personality types. The goal, therefore, is not to abandon active learning, but to diversify the strategies so that shy, quiet, and/or introverted students are not excluded or penalized. Inclusive active learning recognizes that participation can take many forms, and that engagement need not always be vocal or immediate.

2 Activities

This workshop aims to equip engineering educators with practical strategies to foster motivation, confidence, and engagement among shy, quiet, introverted students in engineering programs. By sharing our experiences, we will collect ideas that will help create inclusive learning environments that encourage shy, quiet students' active participation and academic success. The activities in this workshop are:

- (i) Brief discussion on the importance of student engagement and motivation in engineering education.
- (ii) In small teams, participants will discuss which active learning strategies they already use to motivate and engage their shy, quiet, introverted engineering students.
- (iii) In the large group, participants will share the strategies discussed/listed in the small teams. If necessary, the workshop leader will add/complement the list with other strategies.
- (iv) In small teams, participants will be invited to plan a short, safe and supportive active learning segment of a class for shy, quiet, introverted engineering students using one or two of the strategies listed. This planning will be recorded in kraft paper and displayed in the walls of the room where the workshop will be held. Participants will present their plannings.
- (v) Reflecting on the results presented by the small teams.
- (vi) Final remarks.

3 Material needed for the workshop

There is no need for any special materials for this workshop.

4 Expected results

Engineering professors can benefit from a reflexive discussion about the difference between an introverted student, a shy student and a quiet student, and how we can plan interesting active learning classes where these students can participate actively. By the end of this workshop, we expect that the participants will have:

- increased awareness of engagement challenges for shy, quiet, introverted engineering students.
- a bigger menu of active learning strategies and practical tools for fostering shy, quiet, introverted engineering students' engagement, motivation and participation
- greater clarity on the need to promote inclusion in the classroom in engineering education.

This workshop intends to collaborate on empowering educators to unlock the full potential of all engineering students, regardless of their level of extroversion, ensuring a more inclusive and effective learning experience. Afterall, being shy, quiet, or introverted is not a problem to be fixed—it's a difference to be respected and supported.

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